

Building an Evaluation Framework for Innovative Research Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities

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Recognising and evaluating diverse, non-traditional digital scholarly outputs in social sciences and humanities (SSH) is crucial for advancing inclusive and impactful research assessment practices. Aligning with principles from DORA, CoARA, and other international declarations, this presentation proposes **a new framework for evaluating innovative outputs and projects** such as digital monographs, other multimedia materials, datasets, software, and digital tools and platforms. The presentation is delivered by the [OPERAS Innovation Lab](#) – a collaborative initiative dedicated to supporting and advancing innovative services and solutions for scholarly communication in SSH (more about the Lab see: Maryl et al. 2024).

According to the classical economic definition by Joseph Schumpeter, innovation is a practical implementation of ideas that introduce research and accelerate innovation in scholarly communication, new products, services, processes, or even a new organisational structure (Schumpeter, 1934). Within SSH, innovation is about groundbreaking research, novel methodologies, untraditional outputs and advancing scholarly communication (Gulbrandsen & Aanstad, 2014). Novel, digital research outputs and scholarly activities often transcend traditional metrics, requiring nuanced and equitable approaches to capture their full scholarly and societal value (ALLEA 2023). OPERAS has been exploring the intricacies of research assessment based on peer review, seeking to understand its current landscape and potential for innovation (Tóth-Czifra et al. 2021). The research showed its limitations for quality control and assessment of novel research outputs and other scholarly activities.

The evaluation framework builds on international declarations, such as [DORA](#), [CoARA](#), the [Manifesto on Science as a Global Public Good](#), and the [Barcelona Declaration](#), advocating for “bibliodiversity” and the societal impact of research. These agreements underline the importance of integrating innovative outputs into national and international research assessment frameworks. In response to those challenges, initiatives like OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, SSH Open Marketplace, GoTriple, and currently developed GRAPHIA Knowledge

Graphs strive to enhance visibility, accessibility, interdisciplinarity, and collaboration within the scholarly communication ecosystem.

The OPERAS Innovation Lab evaluation framework provides criteria that can be applied during the development process of various innovations. By addressing entrenched issues like resource constraints and traditional peer review's limitations, the Lab aims to reform current assessment systems to better support and reward diverse contributions: 1) innovative projects (service, tool, platform, infrastructure), and 2) innovative research outputs (datasets, software, protocols, multimedia materials, video recording, ephemeral or experimental scholarly outputs, training materials, etc.). The focus of the framework is on evaluating the innovative project as a whole, encompassing the project, service, or tool itself, rather than solely on the content it produces.

The evaluation framework was informed by four case studies that highlighted the challenges and opportunities of fostering innovation within SSH. Shaped during the validation workshop conducted by the OPERAS Innovation Lab team at the [OPERAS Conference in Zadar](#) (24-26 April 2024), it incorporates ten qualitative dimensions to measure and assess innovation in SSH scholarly communication:

1. **Novelty**, understood as the originality of the idea, is not necessarily disruptive, but it changes traditional forms and ways of doing research. The novelty may also lie in repurposing the existing technology and standards for the novel content.
2. **Utility**, defined as addressing a need, answers questions: Is the output/ project responding to a need identified in research practices or the discipline? Will the innovation help specific academic communities?
3. **User engagement** is a criterion for assessing whether an output/ project facilitates user collaboration or contribution. It may include usage metrics or other indicators of community uptake, depending on the nature of the output.
4. **User responsiveness** is a criterion for assessing the ability to deliver a robust, accessible, and adaptable application, service, or tool across various devices and use cases.
5. **Impact and collaboration** measures the capacity to foster science communication and interaction with society, entrepreneurship, knowledge valorisation, and industry-academia cooperation.

6. **Bridging potential** refers to a project or output's capacity to foster multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary approaches, as well as inter-sectoral collaboration. The innovation should enable transgressing boundaries between disciplinary and sectoral knowledge.
7. **Support and training for users** assesses whether the output or project is documented, readily available through training materials, helpdesks or similar measures.
8. **Sustainability** is understood as the capacity to manage the support and maintenance of the innovation (in time) thanks to funding, institutional support (robust infrastructure), human resources, and Open Science policy or rules.
9. **Peer review/evaluation process or workflow.** Open Peer Review is preferred to single/double anonymised, typically used for research outputs and projects. Providing an open and transparent evaluation framework enables better recognition for reviewers, more equity for authors, and a transparent framework for discussing ongoing research.
10. **Reusability/reproducibility** requires that some research results are verifiable and reproducible (data reuse, protocols, workflows under open licences). Is the project's data harvestable by other services and available to other users and projects?

The proposed criteria are aligned with [CoARA](#)'s vision that research assessment should rely primarily on qualitative assessment, for which peer review is central. To properly assess the innovation dimension in a qualitative evaluation process, reviewers should first rely on Open Science requirements such as the FAIR principles and the PID identifiers to ensure the fairness and openness of the project. Considering peer review principles, different dimensions and criteria are expected and required in the parameters and settings of the creative outputs, such as transparency, reuse, actionability, open identities, and responsibility of authors and reviewers.

The application of this framework will be illustrated through four case studies examined by the OPERAS Innovation Lab in 2024: the [SHAPE-ID Toolkit](#), the OAPEN Recommender System, [Transformations: A DARIAH Journal](#), and the [Journal of Digital History](#) (JDH). In addition, the framework will be adapted to assess the GRAPHIA Knowledge Graph platform currently under development. This will offer an opportunity to apply the criteria to a project in progress, highlighting the framework's iterative potential.

A critical takeaway from this presentation is the interplay between research infrastructures and assessment frameworks. Public infrastructures, such as those championed by DARIAH-EU, provide essential support for researchers developing innovative outputs. They also serve as vital platforms for ensuring the sustainability, discoverability, and interoperability of these outputs, in line with Open Science principles. The proposed framework builds on these foundations, emphasising collaboration across disciplines and sectors to drive systemic change in research assessment practices.

By promoting inclusive policies and recognising diverse scholarly contributions, this study aligns with global efforts to transform research assessment into a system that values innovation, equity, and societal relevance. This comprehensive approach aims to inspire policymakers, institutions, and researchers to adopt practices that enrich the evaluation of SSH research and amplify its transformative potential.

The authors used an AI model for proofreading and grammar correction.

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